

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MEHMETAJ****FIRST NAME: BAHRIE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

6 key concepts with page number in text:

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
5. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
6. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)

ESSAY METHODOLOGY

1)INTRODUCTION

To start, an essay is very common exam used wisely in high school or even in college. Moreover, it can be used in the business world, in blogs, in political speeches or advertising. Actually, essay writing is a short-written composition based on research and your own ideas. Furthermore, an essay is designed to convince the reader to accept an idea or a point of view but also, it helps you to communicate information clearly explaining what is important and why it is important.

Nevertheless, writing an essay is not an easy task because you have to sort out the information, you need to focus on the most important ideas. But, sometimes, it can be very hard to do that. For this reason, a lot of work and concentration is required.

So, it would be interesting to know, how can we write a good essay? The answer is simple. First of all, we need to do an important preliminary work (I), then we continue with an effective plan and structure (II) and avoiding the plagiarism (III).

2) AN IMPORTANT PRELIMINARY WORK

First, writing an essay requires a preliminary substantial work. That is to say, “essay writing is not a linear process” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 1). In other words, there are some stages you need to respect. Before starting to write an essay, you should have a clear idea of what you are going to say and how you will build a logical argumentation to answer to your question. So, you should read, research about the topic because just writing what you know it can’t be enough. Reading gives you access to multiple sources of information and during the reading you must take notes with the question clearly in mind (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 2). You can use what you read as evidence to support your ideas.

Once you have the information, you must sort it out. Then, you can draw up a plan deciding which points you will discuss and where you will be focused. Obviously, it is worth giving some thought between the preliminary work and the start of writing because you need to organize your ideas. You need to keep in mind that an essay should be balanced to include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 2) because it can help to understand another perspective of the topic.

Another point is the choice of a writing style. In fact, there are several options you can choose. For example, Turabian Style has two writing styles: author date and notes bibliography. But you can choose other styles too as Oxford style. It depends on the use of American English or British English.

3) AN EFFECTIVE STRUCTURE

An essay should be improved and well - organized. It needs to have a logical structure with an introduction, a body and a conclusion.

Firstly, the introduction should inform the reader of what to expect. It moves from general to specific (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3). Next, it is important to give context which helps the reader to understand the argument. Then you can present the thesis statement which is a sentence that states the main point of a writing essay.

Secondly, the body of the essay is very important because there you present and analyze your ideas and all the information you have gathered during your readings. It consists in paragraphs and “*each paragraph is a building block in the construction of the argument*” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3). Each paragraph should be clear and should introduce a main idea. To make it clearer you can use transition words as firstly, first of all, to start with, then, at first sight, furthermore and so on. You can use relevant examples to support your points of view.

Thirdly, the conclusion is the last paragraph of an essay. Differently from the introduction, it moves from specific to general. It should restate your answer to the question (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3) it ties together your main points and include a final broad

statement (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3). A very important thing to know is that in a conclusion you can not include new arguments or add new evidences because at last you need to show an opening about the topic, something about what implication can have the topic in the future.

To have a clear and good structure you must edit your essay. You should proof-read to improve your first draft.

Moreover, you need to use an academic style being very careful with spelling and punctuation. In that way, you show that you use a formal and written style.

4) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

At first sight, writing an essay may seem easy but is not always because you need to be concentrated, you need to spend time on reading and trying to understand the topic in order to have a sophisticated essay.

The most important thing that the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism. The plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5). It is a serious offense that can have consequences at the university level. For example, a student can have a failing grade, or he can be excluded from university. There are some examples of plagiarism such as quoting, copying and pasting from the internet (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5).

By the way, there are some reasons why the writer plagiarizes. Among them it is the misunderstanding what constitutes plagiarism or when the writer is in panic and the last solution is taking someone's work.

Given that an essay is a combination between a personal work and readings, the writer needs to do an effort to avoid plagiarism. To avoid plagiarism, you should cite the source that has provided the information you are using (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6).

In fact, the writer can cite in -text citation or quoting. This is a way to avoid plagiarism. Nevertheless, using a lot of quotes does not demonstrate a real investment in writing the essay. The writer should use quotations in the right way and not quoting a whole paragraph for example.

5) CONCLUSION

Writing an essay is very interesting but not easy at all. To write a good essay you just need to practice because practising helps you to get better and better. Reading is a way to improve the skills on writing an essay. If you read you can pay attention to word choice, to sentence structure and you will better organize your ideas. A good essay requires you to be original and critical, analyzing and discussing the argument.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed.2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.